

A STUDY ON LEVEL OF EDUCATIONAL ASPIRATIONS AMONG 2ND YEAR STUDENTS OF B.ED. COLLEGES IN MYSORE CITY, INDIA

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Abstract:

This present study was conducted on “A study on Level of Educational Aspiration among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city”, INDIA. The researcher work smoothly and confine the study to specific frame work, the objectives of the study were; to study the level of educational aspirations among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city, to study The significance difference among the following categories with reference to Educational Aspiration: a) Gender (male and female), b) Locality (Urban and Rural), c) Socio-economic Status (high/low socio economic status); d) Types of schools (Government, Private Aided and Private Unaided). Main variables of the study were Educational Aspiration and background variables were Gender, Locality, Socio-economic status and Types of schools. The study was conducted by using Descriptive Survey research methodology to find the degree to which the interaction affect exists among the selected variables. Population of the study was 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges belonging to Government, Private aided and private unaided colleges in Mysore city, Mysore District, Karnataka State. The sample for the study was selected using the proportionate stratified random sampling techniques. The proportion of the sample was selected according to Daryle W. Morgan’s table. In Mysore city there are 37 B.Ed. colleges. According to Morgan’s table 10 colleges were selected out of 37 through lottery system. To collect the required data from the sample of 242 students of B.Ed. colleges the researcher used standard tool “Level of Education Aspiration Test” by Dr. Yasmin Ghani Khan. The research findings were; there is significant difference between male and female of 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges’ in Mysore city with respect to their Levels of Educational Aspiration, no significant difference seen between urban and rural with respect to their Levels of Educational Aspiration among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city, there is significant difference between high and low socio economic status of 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city with respect to their Levels of Educational Aspiration and no significant difference between Government, private aided and private unaided B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city with respect to their Levels of Educational Aspiration. The study recommends the needs to

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investigate separately the educational aspiration, vocational aspiration and economic aspiration etc. of B.Ed. colleges' students and factors determining them in order to have a better understanding of the children and help them to guide in the right direction without losing the most precious resource. Further research may be planned and conducted on the same.

Keywords: educational aspirations, 2nd year students, Mysore City

1. Introduction

Education is a persistent feature characterizing all human societies. In a broader sense, it aims at all round development of personality of the child. In other words education aims at harmonious development of cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains. There are various agencies which contribute at different stages and to different degrees in achieving the said aim.

Education is a process and kind of activity in relation to human beings. It is a continuous effort to develop all capacities of the students to control their neighboring environment and to fulfill their needs. Though education is a part of human life, it cannot help the pursuers unless they have the required amount of Educational Aspirations. Individuals will have aspirations in all stages of life, so that people try for their self enhancement.

The aspirations during student's period influence their behavior. Aspiration of the students is a term used frequently in education. Early research helped us to understand that aspiration as an expression of the will to achieve and improve. Aspiration can be operationally as the student's ability to identify and set goals for the future, while breathing in the present to work toward those goals. This is viewed that the aspiration of the students is the only one that combines the components of his/her motivation (inspiration) in the future (ambitions). An individual's aspiration level represents him not only as he/she is at any particular moment, but also as he/she would like to be at same problem in the future. The term educational aspiration or vocational choice is based on knowledge of traits.

The aspiration level of an individual's is an important motivating factor in his /her career. Level of aspiration is usually influenced by two types of factors. They are: (i) Environmental factors and (ii) personal factors. Environmental factors include determinants like parental ambitions, social expectations, peer pressure, social value, competition, group cohesiveness etc. On the other hand, personal factors play dominant role in determining his level of aspiration as the child grows older and become more aware of his abilities and interests. These personal factors include determinants such as wishes, personality, past experiences, values, interests, sex, socio-economic background. The dimensions of aspiration are Career Aspiration, Social Aspiration, Economic Aspiration, Personal Aspiration and Educational Aspiration.

2. Literature Review

Parent's involvement in Childs early education is consistently found to be positively associated with a child's academic performance (Hara & Baurke, 1998, Hill & Craft, 2003, Marcon 1999, Stevenson & Baker, 1987). Specifically, children whose parents are more involved in their education have higher levels of academic performance than children whose parents are involved to a lesser degree.

Investigations of the relationship between parental aspirations and their children's Academic outcomes have demonstrated that educational success can be significantly influenced by parental aspirations (Fehrmann, Keith and Reimers, 1987; Ho and Willms, 1996; Ritchie, Flouri, and Buchanan, 2005).

Glass (1974), studied birth order, verbal intelligence and educational aspirations over 2523 students of higher socio-economic and background 10th and 12th grade and found that first born children were superior to later born in a test of reading ability and also found that first born children had higher educational aspirations than later-born children.

Dunne, Elliott and Carlsen (1979), studied sex difference in the educational and occupational Aspiration of rural youth over 926 girls and 861 boys of grade 10th, 11th and 12th. It was found that female significantly higher educational aspirations, the same or higher occupational aspiration, and equal ranges of job choices.

Klailat, Ahlam (1981), conducted a study on "relationship of socioeconomic status to the educational aspirations for sixth and ninth grade pupils". The findings of the study was all the mediating variables, grades and parental encouragement consistently had the largest effects, and background variables do not have a direct effects but are mediated through the social psychological variables. In general, more of the variance in educational aspirations can be explained by grades, sex and nationality. Gupta, M. (1987). Conducted study on "A Study of Relationship between Locus of Control, Anxiety, Level of Aspiration and Academic Achievement of Secondary Students", D. Phil, Education, Allahabad University, 1987.

Rajput (1989) conducted a study on the "educational aspiration and academic achievement of secondary school students" With the objective to examine the influence of family factors on the academic achievement of adolescents. By taking a sample of 1000 higher secondary school students through stratified random sampling technique and found that the academic achievement of students was influenced in proportion to their parental encouragement; there Review of Related Literature 20 was Pareek, D.L (1990) conducted a study on self-concept, personality traits and aspirations of the adolescents studying in Central schools, state government schools and private schools in Rajasthan found that there existed no significant relationship between personality traits and level of aspiration among students from different types of schools..

Das, D.G (1991) conducted a study on "educational and vocational aspiration level of tribal and non-tribal youth of the south Gujarat". Gujarat region found that there was no significant difference of socioeconomic status with respect to locality on educational and vocational aspiration levels.

Claudia Buchmann, Ben Dalton (2002) conducted a study on “Interpersonal Influences and educational aspirations in 12 countries. The results indicate that peers and parents influence educational aspirations in countries with relatively undifferentiated secondary schooling, like the United States, while the influence of significant others is negligible in societies with more differentiated secondary education. In these latter systems, it appears that aspirations are largely determined by the type of school the student attends; there is little room for interpersonal effects. The effects of significant others on students’ aspirations depend, in large part, on the structural features of the educational systems in which they operate.

Schoon and Parsons (2002) used longitudinal data from the 1970 British Birth Cohort to investigate the adult attainment of socially advantaged and disadvantaged sixteen year-olds. While socially disadvantaged youths were found to be at risk of educational failure parental aspirations were found to constitute a protective factor associated with resilience. Children’s career aspirations and expectations have been found to reflect those of their parents, and in particular seem to be influenced by the mother (Otto, 2000). Although the influence of parents seems to be mediated by peer influence (Palmonari, Kirchler and Pombeni, 1991).

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Sampling

242 respondents were selected for this study. Sex, age, level of education and experience were important parameters considered in the sample selection.

3.2 Sources of Data Collection

a. Primary sources

A well-planned and structured questionnaire was presented to the sample selected. Data confidentiality was well considered.

b. Secondary Sources

Relevant information from past records, newspapers, articles and booklets were collected and reviewed to establish the gap that existed.

3.3 Tools and Techniques for Data Collection

Questionnaires, interviews and observation were the important tools for collecting data. Books, reports, journals and articles that were relevant to the study were reviewed and studied. Dishonest and incomplete information were discarded.

3.4 Plan of Analysis

Data was well-tabulated and corresponding percentage given. Tables and graphs were used to get accurate information. Inappropriate and biased responses were discarded.

3.5 Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Table 4.1: The level of Educational Aspiration among
 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city, India

S/N	Level of Educational Aspiration	N	%
1	High (above S.D + Mean)	43	17.8
2	Low (below S.D +Mean)	199	82.2
	Total	242	100

4. Analysis

Table 4.1 Shows that 17.8% 43 out of 242, 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges have high level Educational Aspiration while 82.2% 199 out of 242, 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city have low Educational Aspiration. This means that there is high percentage (82.2%) of students with Low Levels of Educational Aspiration among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city.

Graph 4.1: The level of Educational Aspiration among
 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city, India

4.1.1 Interpretation

This figure shows that 17.8 % of 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city have high level of Educational Aspiration while 82.2% of 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city have low level of Educational Aspiration. This means that there is high percentage (82.2%) of students with Low Levels of Educational Aspiration among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city.

Table 4.2: The difference between male and female of 2nd year students of B.Ed.
 colleges in Mysore city with reference to Educational Aspiration

S/N	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-Value	df	Remarks
1	Male	86	12.00	5.71	5.94	240	Rejected 0.05 level
2	Female	156	16.28	5.15			

4.2.1 Analysis

Table 4.3 shows that the obtained t-value 5.94 is greater than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 significant level for degree of freedom 240. So Null hypothesis is rejected. This means

that there is statistically significant difference between male and female students of B.Ed. colleges with respect to their level of Educational Aspiration. Hence, the researcher constructed alternate null hypothesis “There is significant difference between male and female with reference to Educational Aspiration among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city”.

Graph: 4.3: The difference between male and female of 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city with reference to Educational Aspiration

4.3.1 Interpretation

This figure shows difference between male and female with respect to Educational Aspiration among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city. This means that male students have Mean of 12 while female students have Mean of 16.28. Null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, the researcher concluded that there is significant difference between male and female with reference to Educational Aspiration among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city.

Table 4.4: The difference between urban and rural among students of B.Ed. colleges with reference to Educational Aspiration

S/N	Locality	N	Mean	SD	t-value	df	Remarks
1	Urban	186	14.62	5.99	0.717	240	Accepted 0.05 level
2	Rural	56	15.25	4.77			

4.4.1 Analysis

Table 4.2.2 Shows that the obtained t-value 0.717 is less than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 significant level for degree of freedom 240 null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no statistically significant difference between urban and rural students of B.Ed. colleges with respect to their level of Educational Aspiration among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city. Hence, null hypothesis is accepted.

Graphs: 4.4: Shows the difference between urban and rural among students of B.Ed. colleges with reference to Educational Aspiration

4.5.1 Interpretation

This figure shows difference between Urban and Rural with respect to their Levels of Educational Aspiration among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city. This means that students from Urban have Mean of 14.62 while those from Rural have Mean of 15.25. Null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no statistically significant difference between urban and rural students of B.Ed. colleges with respect to their level of Educational Aspiration among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city.

Table 4.5: The difference between high socio economic status and low socio economic status of 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city with reference to Educational Aspiration

S/N	SES	N	Mean	SD	t-value	df	Remarks
1	Above 250,000	191	14.23	5.88	2.901	240	Rejected 0.05 level
2	Below 250,000	51	16.80	4.60			

4.6.1 Analysis

Table 4.5 shows that the obtained t-value 2.901 is greater than the t-table figure 1.96 the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is statistically significant difference between high socio economic status and low socio economic status with respect to their level of Educational Aspiration among students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city. The researcher constructed alternate hypothesis "There is significant difference between high socio economic status and low socio economic status with reference to Educational Aspiration among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city"

Graphs: 4.5: Shows the difference between high socio economic status and low socio economic status of 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city with reference to Educational Aspiration

4.7.1 Interpretation

This figure shows difference between high and low socio economic status with respect to their level of Educational Aspiration among students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city. This mean that students with high level of socio economic status (above 2, 50,000) have Mean of 14.23 while those with low socio economic status (below 2, 50,000) have mean of 16.8. This means that there is statistically significant difference between high socio economic status and low socio economic status with respect to their level of Educational Aspiration among students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city. The Null hypothesis is rejected. Hence the researcher constructed alternate hypothesis “There is significant difference between high socio economic status and low socio economic status with reference to Educational Aspiration among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city”.

Table 4.6: Shows the one-way ANOVA for the mean scores of Government, Private Aided and Private Unaided students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city with reference to Educational Aspiration

S/N	Types of School	N	Mean	SD	f	df	Remarks
1	Government	78	15.13	6.012	0.571	239	Accepted 0.05 level
2	Private aided	70	15.03	5.873			
3	Private unaided	94	14.28	5.387			

4.8.1 Analysis

Table 4.6 shows that the obtained f-value 0.571 is less than f-table value 2.60 the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no statistically significant difference between types of schools with respect to their level of Educational Aspiration among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city. Hence null hypothesis is accepted

Graphs: 4.6: Shows one way ANOVA for the mean scores of Government, Private Aided and Private Unaided students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city with reference to Educational Aspiration

4.8.2 Interpretation

This figure shows difference between types of schools with respect to their Levels of Educational Aspiration among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city. This shows that student from government colleges have Mean of 15.13, students from private aided colleges have Mean of 15.03 and those from private unaided have Mean of 14.28. This means that there is no statistically significant difference between types of schools with respect to their level of Educational Aspiration among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

5. Conclusions and Recommendation

We cannot ignore the fact that education is the most important input of development. The overall progress of any country depends on its improvement in education. Therefore, it is essential to understand the greater and active participation of parents, teachers and above all the community in the educational process of the society.

The research had raft of findings that there is significant difference between male and female of 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges' in Mysore city with respect to their Levels of Educational Aspiration. Other findings indicate that there is no significant difference seen between urban and rural with respect to their Levels of Educational Aspiration among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city, there is significant difference between high and low socio economic status of 2nd year students of B.Ed. Colleges in Mysore city with respect to their Levels of Educational Aspiration and no significant difference between Government, private aided and private unaided B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city with respect to their Levels of Educational Aspiration.

The research is bound to be helpful to the various actors of education. Regardless of their environmental orientation, the motivation to acquire education remains the same. Educational stakeholders should put more effort in enriching the environment for the rural The research findings were; there is significant difference between male and female of 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges' in Mysore city with respect to their Levels of Educational Aspiration, no significant difference seen between urban and rural with

respect to their Levels of Educational Aspiration among 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city, there is significant difference between high and low socio economic status of 2nd year students of B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city with respect to their Levels of Educational Aspiration and no significant difference between Government, private aided and private unaided B.Ed. colleges in Mysore city with respect to their Levels of Educational Aspiration. So, no group is disadvantaged.

5.1 Recommendations

The research recommends the following;

- 1) Proper establishment of career guidance service in schools and colleges to enable the students to have a clear job description and expectation in an effort to address role ambiguity and conflict.
- 2) Establish healthy communication between teachers and students to provide educational and psychological support.
- 3) Regular invitation of resource person or role model in the community to address and inspire student more on their aspiration.
- 4) Psychological input courses should be put in place for remedial treatment to the anxiety and low educational aspiration students.
- 5) The schools administrators should put in place mechanisms for removing or reducing anxiety creators and promote friendly and conducive environment for learning to take place.
- 6) The teachers and administrators should plan suitable curriculum and provide effective learning facilities and innovative methods and techniques in the classroom according to the aspiration and anxieties of students particularly of the students of higher secondary course which is considered crucial in determining their future career.
- 7) Students who have high Educational Aspirations are more likely to take advantage of educational opportunities that may lead to academic success. Likewise, students with low Educational Aspirations are less likely to take advantage of these opportunities, thus limiting their future educational opportunities.
- 8) Educationists, governments and policymakers have to realize the importance of one's expectations of the outcome and not only for children themselves, but also for family, teachers and the community in order to help them to support their kids, students and friends so, the children can realize their potential and expectations.
- 9) A further study is recommended on the level of anxiety.

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